

*Market Uptake Measures of Floating Offshore Wind Technology
Systems (FOWTs)*

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MARINEWIND project aims to identify challenges and potential opportunities for enhancing the role of floating offshore wind technology in innovative system integration solutions. The project will explore market dynamics, policy and regulatory issues, social considerations, financial aspects, techno-economic solutions, and recommendations for storage and flexibility provisions.

This report presents the outcomes of the first co-creation workshop in Portugal. A total of 22 stakeholders of the wind sector from different backgrounds participated in the event. All the participants contributed to identifying the main barriers and opportunities that exist in Portugal for the growth of floating wind in the country, taking into account social, environmental, technological, and financial aspects.

The Portuguese government is actively working towards aligning its port legislation to current trends, emphasizing the simplification of procedures, the promotion of innovation, and a commitment to increased sustainability. As part of this initiative, the government is exploring flexible concession models for port areas, aiming to accommodate both offshore activities and traditional port functions. This adaptation seeks to create an adequate environment to the development of wind farms and other sustainable industries within national ports.

The discussions about the main enablers and barriers identified a clear regulatory framework as the most important enabler, followed by technological maturity. On the opposite, the audience views the establishment of appropriate and sufficient infrastructure (e.g., ports) as the primary barrier to foster floating offshore wind projects in Portugal, and fishing and navigation as the most conflicting activities.

The results of these discussions will be incorporated into the MARINEWIND web-based Geographical Information System (webGIS). This system will offer customized information about Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWT) to stakeholders based on their category, location, and objectives. The system will also offer policy recommendations for informed Renewable Energy Sources (RES) policies and strategies to enhance societal acceptance (WP4). The Replicability Plan will facilitate the transfer of knowledge.

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1 EVENT DETAILS

EVENT LOCATION: Headquarters of the Aveiro Port Authority, Aveiro

EVENT DATE: 24th October 2023 14:30-16:30

EVENT TITLE: Measures to Boost the Floating Offshore Wind Energy Market in Portugal

TYPE OF EVENT: Physical

CATEGORY OF THE EVENT: Co-creation Workshop

EVENT AFFILIATION: None

LEAD ORGANISER: WavEC Offshore Renewables

LANGUAGE: Portuguese

CONCEPT: The workshop targeted to bring together industry leaders, experts, and stakeholders to discuss and explore effective market measures for the rapid expansion of floating offshore wind projects in Portugal through the analysis of the potential barriers and enablers. The event aimed to strengthen collaboration between industry, academia, authorities, and the port sector, to accelerate and ensure the secure advancement of the floating wind industry towards successful commercial implementation.

OBJECTIVES

The workshop's specific objectives were to identify barriers and enablers to enhance the floating offshore wind market in Portugal by discussing the results of the Working Group for the "Planning and operation of power stations based on renewable energy sources of ocean origin or location", focusing on the Subgroup 3 Report "Planning the development of port infrastructures to support the implementation of offshore renewable energy sources".

The first co-creation workshop in Portugal was designed to contribute to the objectives of the MARINEWIND project:

- Increase awareness of FOWTs via co-creation activities that directly engage policy and decision makers, market and business actors, civil society organisations and funding bodies.
- Encourage social acceptance by directly involving local communities and fishermen and addressing environmental issues.
- Facilitate communication and collaboration among all the stakeholders directly and indirectly involved in the Portuguese MARINEWIND Lab.

TARGET AUDIENCE

The event targeted representatives of industry, research institutes, public authorities, supply chains, civil society, green innovation and policy and regulatory entities involved in the floating offshore wind sector.

For each specific category, the initial targeted audience included participants from:

- Industry: technology and project developers.
- Supply chain: port infrastructure, cable design and installation, tech/project developers, and trade associations, O&M services.
- Scientific & research community.
- Public authorities: at national level and maritime transport authorities.
- Policy/Regulatory: regulatory bodies at national level.
- Civil society: civil society organisations, and citizens.
- Green innovation: SMEs, ecologists.

AGENDA:

- 14:30-14:35 Welcome
- 14:35-15:00 Presentation on the results of the Working Group for the “Planning and operation of power stations based on renewable energy sources of ocean origin or location - Report of Subgroup 3” by Dr. Eduardo Feio, Chairman of the Board of Directors of the Port of Aveiro
- 15:00-15:15 Presentation of the European MARINEWIND project by Janete Gonçalves, Communication and Dissemination Coordinator of the project
- 15:15-15:45 Coffee Break
- 15:45-16:25 Discussion and integration of the study's results into the European MARINEWIND project – Co-creation activity moderated by Prof. António Sarmento
- 16:25-16:30 Closing

PARTICIPANTS OF YOUR EVENT:

Figure 1 shows the target audience for the 1st Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal, and Figure 2 shows the final audience that participated in the event.

Figure 1. Initial target audience for the 1st Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal.

Figure 2. Participants of the 1st Co-creation MARINEWIND Workshop in Portugal.

2 OVERVIEW OF CONTRIBUTIONS AND INTERVENTIONS BY THE SPEAKERS

2.1 Relevance of the topics addressed in the 1st Workshop in Portugal in the national floating offshore wind context

Within an energy policy framework that prioritizes achieving a balance between supply security, environmental sustainability, and economic feasibility, Portugal has underscored the exploration of offshore wind resources. This commitment to offshore wind is rooted in the success of the Windfloat and Windfloat Atlantic initiatives. The first was a full-scale pilot project resulting from a collaboration between EDP and Principle Power Inc. (PPI) and consisted of a 2 MW wind turbine mounted on a semi-submersible floating platform developed by PPI, and was installed in 2011 off the coast of Póvoa de Varzim. This project proved the viability of the technology and was subsequently replicated on a pre-commercial scale with the Windfloat Atlantic project, marking the first world's semi-submersible offshore wind farm, installed in 2019 off the coast of Viana do Castelo. With a total capacity of 25 MW (comprising 3 turbines each with a nominal power of 8.4 MW), WindFloat Atlantic not only set a significant precedent as the world's first semi-submersible technology-based floating wind farm but also acted as the catalyst for an emerging offshore energy cluster in Portugal.

In view of recent floating offshore wind technological advances, in which Portugal has played a leading role, the Portuguese government has set itself the ambition of achieving an installed capacity of floating offshore wind of 10 GW by 2030. To meet the targets of decarbonizing the economy and the energy sector by 2050¹, the decision to install 10 GW of floating technologies by 2030 through auctions is driven by the constraints imposed by the Portuguese continental shelf. Due to its narrow width and rapid increase in depth near the coastline, it's unfeasible to install wind farms using conventional fixed foundations, typically placed at depths ranging from 30 to 60 m.

To support the development of offshore wind energy, licenses must be awarded by the Directorate-General for Energy and Geology (DGEG) and Grid Capacity Reserve titles are managed by the Public Electrical Grid (RESP). The Directorate-General for Natural Resources (DGRM) handles permits for maritime space use, which are given in conjunction with Grid Capacity Reserve titles. Although Portugal aims to initiate a phased offshore wind power auction in the last quarter of 2023, the existing regulatory framework does not contain specific provisions for floating offshore wind farms.

To plan and operationalize renewable energy centres from oceanic resources in response to the climate crisis, a Working Group was formed by the Government order no. 11404/2022, of 23 September. The Working Group developed an approach that minimised risks for developers and maximises economic value for society regarding offshore renewable energy sources, especially floating wind power. The Working Group was divided into three Sub-groups, each of them with the following objectives:

1. Preliminary proposal for spatialised areas and points for connection to the National Electricity Transmission Network.
2. Identification of models for awarding TRC and associated TUPEM licences, based on international benchmarking; and study of technical and investment models for the

¹ Roadmap to Carbon Neutrality 2050 (RNC2050) ([ficheiro.aspx\(portugal.gov.pt\)](https://www.ficheiro.aspx(portugal.gov.pt)))

development of the offshore and onshore electrical infrastructure required for the start-up of offshore renewable power generation centres.

3. Planning the development of port infrastructures to support the implementation of offshore renewable energy sources.

The Working Group created a Final Report² that integrates the results of the three Sub-groups. The Report presents a preliminary proposal for specialized areas that went through a period of public consultation. The initial proposal was updated based on the feedback received from the fishing sector.

Two competitive models were also identified for the development of offshore wind energy in Portugal: a centralised one with a mechanism to support electricity production, and another decentralised without such a mechanism. These two models can be implemented individually or together, simultaneously, or sequentially.

In addition, the Working Group studied architectural alternatives for the offshore electricity grid, considering costs, reliability, environmental impacts and impacts on other maritime and land-based activities. Preliminary analyses were also made of locations for interconnection points with the onshore grid and the development needs of port infrastructures were identified, with emphasis on the specialization of each port in the construction and maintenance of future wind farms.

The final recommendations of the Final Report are:

1. Provide 3.5 GW available through competitive procedures in Viana do Castelo, Leixões and Figueira da Foz, and allocate the remaining 6.5 GW in later phases until 2030.
2. Continue to develop the offshore wind energy market in Portugal under a competitive model, regardless of centralisation and the remuneration model.
3. Start the first competitive procedure by the end of 2023 with a pre-qualification phase³ of at least three months.
4. Utilise a network architecture with high-voltage substations of the national transmission network (RNT) supported by fixed platforms on the seabed to reduce the number of cables between maritime areas and land.
5. Develop a strategy to boost the offshore wind energy industry, including a preliminary analysis of the national and international scenario.

The MARINEWIND project aims to assess each country Labs context in terms of barriers and opportunities for floating offshore wind energy projects. The relevance of the Working Group's findings for ocean renewable energy projects in Portugal, particularly in the context of offshore wind energy, prompted the organization of the 1st Workshop in Portugal. This Workshop focused on discussing the Working Group's results and served as a platform for event-related discussions centered around the Final Report.

² Report of the Working Group for the Planning and operation of power stations based on renewable energy sources of ocean origin or location (ineg.pt/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/20230531-GTOffshore_RelatorioFinal_vfinal.pdf)

³ The Announcement No. 220-A/2023 was published on the 30th October, formalizing the kickoff of the Portuguese offshore wind pre-qualification phase with the initial stage for the Expression of Interest ([Anúncio n.º 220-A/2023 | DR \(diariodarepublica.pt\)](https://diariodarepublica.pt)).

2.2 Results of the Working Group for the “Planning and operation of power stations based on renewable energy sources of ocean origin or location - Report of Subgroup 3”

The Working Group discussed the opportunity presented by the energy transition for European ports, with a focus on Portugal and its strategic position in the Atlantic. The country has made significant strides in renewable energy, particularly in offshore wind, with projects like WindFloat and WindFloat Atlantic and the plan for the 10GW offshore wind auction.

The changing landscape of the Portuguese ports is driven by two key factors: energy transition and digital transition. The Portuguese government aims to adapt port legislation to current trends, simplifying procedures, promoting innovation, and increasing sustainability.

The Working Group dedicated to the energy transition in ports plays a crucial role. It is tasked with proposing maritime zones for offshore wind projects, developing the technical framework for electrical networks, and assessing infrastructure needs for the construction of wind farms. The group's first phase involved proposing areas for wind park development, with subsequent steps including port development planning, industrial planning, network development, and auction design. The government is considering flexible concession models for port areas to accommodate both offshore activities and traditional port functions.

The energy transition not only involves decarbonizing port operations by replacing polluting equipment but also aims to create new industries within national ports. This includes attracting offshore wind industry, establishing renewable fuel production for transportation, and reinforcing the naval industry. The emphasis is on green maritime transport through the creation of green corridors and the use of renewable fuels.

In the upcoming phases of this initiative, the Portuguese government, in collaboration with port administrations, is actively assessing the implementation of flexible concession models for port areas. This approach aims to smoothly accommodate the development of both offshore activities and traditional port functions. The focus on developing the industrial offshore value chain and port infrastructure is positioned as a precursor to the deployment of wind farms, ultimately contributing to achieving a lower Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE) through a robust industrial strategy. Additionally, port authorities are set to initiate public tenders to attract new industrial projects to the port zones, showcasing a commitment to fostering innovation and growth in the sector.

2.3 Presentation of the European MARINEWIND project

The presentation of the MARINEWIND project was conducted by Janete Gonçalves (WavEC). The following topics were included and presented during this part of the event:

- Composition of the MARINEWIND Consortium.
- Ambition of the project.
- Methodology and duration of the project.
- Location of the 5 Labs (Portugal, UK, Greece, Italy, and Spain), highlighting the importance of the different developing phases in the implementation of FOWTs of each country, and how it is expected that Labs will support the transfer of knowledge from the established experiences to

the potential FOWT sites where plans for installation of FOWT are still at various stages of planning or implementation.

- Presentation of the most relevant projects or initiatives of each Lab.
- Introduction to the Co-creation activity in the MENTIMETER Tool.

3 CO-CREATION ACTIVITY

A survey was prepared by APRE, RSE, CNR and UoY on the MENTIMETER Tool to be submitted to all the participants during the first Workshop events of the MARINEWIND Labs. This data collection exercise was intended to provide an insightful data of participants' experiences and insights regarding barriers and enablers for the implementation of floating offshore wind in Portugal.

This activity was included and designed in the 1st Co-creation Workshop in Portugal to encourage the formulation of additional questions to the audience, to broaden the discussion on the barriers and opportunities facing the floating wind energy market in Portugal and other relevant information about Portugal in the context of the European MARINEWIND project.

3.1 Results of the survey

Question 1 - Which of the following categories represents you?

Figure 3. MENTIMETER Tool Question 1 results.

The question regarding the category to which the participants belonged highlighted a greater audience from the business sector (67%), followed by an overall balance in the participation between institutions (11%), associations (11%), and universities & research centres (6%) and “other” category (6%).

Question 2 - What are the most important enabling factors to invest in FOWTs?

Figure 4. MENTIMETER Tool Question 2 results.

This question received votes from 17 participants and the majority (41%) agreed that a “clear regulatory framework” is the most important enabling factor to invest in FOWTs, followed by “technological maturity” (24%), “supply chain” (18%), “incentives” (12%) and “market share and demand” (6%). The “grid design” didn’t receive any votes.

Question 3 - In your opinion, which of these risks is most significant to your value chain?

Figure 5. MENTIMETER Tool Question 3 results.

The “development of adequate infrastructures (e.g., ports)” was the most significant risk associated with the value chain chosen by the audience with 11 votes out of 18 (61%). “Local level supply chain capacity” and “availability of ad hoc vessels for the installation of the turbines” got similar results, representing 22% and 17% of the votes, respectively.

Question 4 - In Portugal, what aspects could encourage the increase in FOWTs in a sustainable way, respecting other uses of the sea?

Figure 6. MENTIMETER Tool Question 4 results.

In this open question regarding what aspects could promote an increase of floating offshore wind in Portugal, but in a sustainable way and respecting other users of the sea, there were 15 answers. Clear communication with all the communities, informing and educating them about offshore wind, and clear legislation were common answers.

One participant also suggested the use of biohubs and the implementation of artificial reefs to promote the development of marine life and therefore enhance fishing activities, which would increase the acceptance and interest in FOWTs by the fishing sector.

The integration of professionals from traditional sectors, like fishing or naval repairs and construction, in operation and maintenance activities, as well as in monitoring activities, and handing incentives to the fishing and tourism sectors were also mentioned.

Question 5 - What other uses of the sea should be considered when planning the expansion of offshore wind energy for a conscious and shared development?

Aquacultura	Captura de carbono	Aquacultura
Offset de carbono	Monitorização e observação oceânica	Pesca, aquacultura, vias marítimas, preservação do ecossistemas
Recifes artificiais, pescas com artes compatíveis, aquacultura, wave energy, turismo	Pesca	Todos os que não tenham conflitos identificados
Recurso a outras fontes de energia oceânicas	Energia das ondas	Outras formas de aproveitamento de energia
Pesca	Defesa e soberania do nosso espaço marítimo	Utilização conjunta com outras tecnologias offshore, vide Corpower. Aquicultura offshore.
Necessidade de manutenção (ex. towing no caso de flutuante)	Pesca, produção de algas, aquacultura, diferentes tecnologias de energias das ondas	

Figure 7. MENTIMETER Tool Question 5 results.

This open question collected 17 responses, of which the most common were “fishing”, “aquaculture”, and “other forms of offshore energy production”, like wave energy. “Tourism”, “artificial reefs”, “maintenance needs”, and “maritime space defence” were also mentioned.

Question 6 - What do you consider important to actively involve the civil society?

Figure 8. MENTIMETER Tool Question 6 results.

The words most commonly used to describe what is important to actively involve civil society in the debate around the expansion of floating offshore wind in Portugal were all related to educating and informing: “transparency”, “information”, “communication”, “education”, “dialogue”, etc. The price of

electricity and the creation of jobs was also mentioned as factors that would increase interest in civil society to actively engage in the process of implementation of more FOWTs in Portugal.

Question 7 - Which activity is the most conflicting with the offshore wind sector?

Figure 9. MENTIMETER Tool Question 7 results.

Regarding which activity is most conflicting with the offshore wind sector, “fishing” got the first place, followed by “shipping”, which was closely followed by “environmental protection”. “Tourism” came in fourth place.

Question 8 - Which activity is most compatible with the floating offshore wind sector?

Figure 10. MENTIMETER Tool Question 8 results.

When asked about which activity is most compatible with the floating offshore wind sector, 53% of the audience agreed with “environmental protection”. 18% said “shipping”, 24% said “fishing” and “other” (12% each), and 6% voted for “tourism”.

4 DISCUSSIONS TOPICS OVERVIEW

The presentation from Dr. Eduardo Feio about the results of the Working Group for the “Planning and operation of power stations based on renewable energy sources of ocean origin or location - Report of Subgroup 3” opened a discussion about the needs of development of the Portuguese port infrastructures to achieve the country's ambition of having 10 GW of offshore wind by 2030.

According to Dr. Eduardo Feio, the need to produce this Report and the consequent creation of this Working Group were fundamental to initiating dialogue between the Portuguese ports and the naval and offshore industries about the challenges ahead. There is now more awareness of the risks and

what needs to be done to achieve the proposed goal launched by the Portuguese Government than two years ago.

One of the participants, Pedro Teixeira, consultant at MDS Global Insurance & Risk Consultants, raised his concern about what Portugal has to offer regarding port hubs and compared it with Scotland, Norway, and Spain. This initiated a debate around the Portuguese challenges to becoming a competitor in this sector. Dr. Eduardo Feio mentioned that the North countries had the advantage of starting this process earlier when facing the challenge of bottom-fixed offshore wind, which allowed them to develop their ports, industries, policies, etc., that can now be adapted to the floating offshore wind. This was not the case for Portugal, as bottom-fixed offshore wind was not an option, bringing us to start facing those challenges just now. Dr. Eduardo Feio added that it is indeed crucial to develop port infrastructure to speed up the Portuguese development of floating offshore wind, allowing the country to be competitive, but this needs to be a collective effort between society, government, academia, the supply chain, among other sectors.

Pedro Teixeira highlighted the importance to have cooperation between Portuguese ports, a essential cooperation that is mirrored in the Report as one of the main conclusions.

Additionally, with the aim of making the event more dynamic and promoting the participation of all attendees, it was decided not to include a formal roundtable section in the agenda. Instead, an analysis of the results was performed during the Co-creation activity by Prof. António Sarmento and additional questions were addressed to all participants.

During the Workshop, participants found themselves in substantial agreement on most of the discussed topics. The diverse backgrounds of the attendees brought forth interesting perspectives from various areas, yet remarkably, the input remained consistently aligned. The convergence of viewpoints underscored a shared understanding and consensus among the participants, reflecting a harmonious exchange of ideas and a cohesive collaborative effort during the Workshop discussions.

Fortunately, we were privileged to have a participant with expertise in the insurance sector during the event, particularly when addressing uncertainties raised by an attendee regarding sea insurance in response to Question 5 concerning other users of the sea. The question addressed the possible concern of insurance companies when considering fishing as another use of the maritime space together with floating offshore wind. Activities such as fishing or aquaculture could present a risk to offshore wind farms, which would be the main asset of the maritime space once implemented. Prof. António Sarmento commented that if insurance companies consider that complementary activities represent a high risk, there will consequently be a rise in the premium and it may not be advantageous from the point of view of the economic viability of the enterprise. Pedro Teixeira pointed out that, even though each risk must be evaluated, and each incident must be analysed case by case, most accidents have to do with carrier cables and ship cables during operation phases, and usually do not have relation with other activities.

In addressing the question of conflicting activities with the offshore wind sector, fishing emerged as the primary concern, securing the top spot in the rankings. Following closely behind were shipping and environmental protection, with tourism occupying the fourth position. Notably, conflicts with

fishermen were highlighted as a significant concern in Portugal, while the moderator indicated that the impact of the other mentioned activities is comparatively less pronounced.

5 SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED BARRIERS AND ENABLERS

The table below summarises the main barriers, criticalities and bottlenecks identified during the Workshop on the left column, and the most significant enablers and incentives on the right column.

BARRIERS	ENABLERS
Complex and non-digital licensing processes.	Recent advances in Portugal to create a clearer regulatory framework for the implementation of offshore wind projects.
No suitable infrastructure for the implementation of large floating offshore wind projects. Necessity of port infrastructure adaption.	Economic advantages for local and national enterprises of any direct participation in the supply chain.
Lack of enough internal technical capacity to meet the future needs of the offshore wind industry.	Use the maritime zones granted for wind farms also for the implementation of other forms of renewable energy or other activities (multiuse concept).
No territorial planning reconciling the interests of various sectors and eliminating possible conflicts.	National planning supporting the implementation of offshore wind energy on the medium and long term.
Not enough public investment oriented to achieve energetic independence and a sustainable growth of the country.	Adaptation of existing port infrastructure to foster the development of offshore wind industry and preventive investment in new infrastructure.
Fishing and tourism are important sectors of the country. To counterbalance negative effects and opposition against the implementation of offshore wind projects, compensatory measures for these sectors might be implemented.	Success record on previous floating wind projects.
Lack of technological maturity (floating platform, dynamic cables, etc.)	Education and information for public acceptance.
	Environment sanctuaries that promote biodiversity created by wind farms when no

	other activities are allowed in the wind farm maritime space.
	Possibility of promoting other activities within a co-existence approach of the maritime space such as carbon capture, aquaculture, ocean monitoring and observation or environmental protection.

Final thoughts:

Between the realization of the Workshop and the submission of this report, it was announced on the 30th October the opening of the initial stage for the Portuguese offshore wind pre-qualification phase with the Expression of Interest ([Anúncio n.º 220-A/2023 | DR \(diariodarepublica.pt\)](https://diariodarepublica.pt)). This represents an important step for the implementation of floating offshore wind projects in the country. The evolution of the floating offshore wind market in Portugal will be followed closely within the MARINEWIND project and analysed in future workshops.